

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR AND RATE-DEPENDENT PROPERTIES OF ARAMID FIBRE/CARBON FIBRE HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The flexural behaviour of composite beams depends on both the tensile and the compressive properties of the reinforcement. Hence, this behaviour is markedly affected by the great difference between the tensile and the compressive strengths of organic fibre-reinforced composites. The bending behaviour of such materials is dominated by their premature yielding in compression at the compression face, as a result of the low compressive strength of the fibre. Concerning this property the present study adds preliminary investigations of the fatigue behaviour of hybrid composite materials in flexure in two different directions:

- (i) An experimental investigation of hybrid effects in the *S-N* trends, as a function of the fibre types and structure of the material.
- (ii) A study of the rate-dependent flexural behaviour and of its correlation with the fatigue life.

The results show that aramid fibre/carbon fibre hybrids of the ACA type, namely, sandwich hybrids with aramid fibre-reinforced skins and carbon fibre-reinforced core, exhibit a positive hybrid effect in their flexural strength. The high flexural strength of these hybrids is reflected in their higher fatigue stress too, although the fatigue life itself is given by a linear rule of mixtures from the properties of the parent materials. The advantage of the fatigue behaviour of the ACA hybrids is underlined by the inferiority of the CAC materials.

It is suggested that the reason for the positive hybrid effect in the flexural fatigue of the ACA hybrids may lay with the strain rate-dependence of failure in these materials. With compressive failure being the active mode of failure in these materials under both static and fatigue conditions, the respective properties are expected to be a direct function of the compressive strength, which in turn is extremely strain rate dependent.

INTRODUCTION

The flexural behaviour of composite beams depends on both the tensile and the compressive properties of the reinforcement. In a series of studies of the bending behaviour of aramid fibre-reinforced composite and hybrid beams [1-4], various consequences pertinent to the low compressive strength of these materials have been examined experimentally, and explained theoretically, assuming that an elastic/plastic stress distribution in the tensile/compressive sides of the beam, respectively, follows the yielding in the compressive side.

The present research takes the investigation of the flexural behaviour of aramid fibre-reinforced composite and hybrid beams an additional step forward, in attempting to study the fatigue and time-dependent properties of these materials. Again, attention is placed on the effect of the low compressive strength of the aramid fibre.

Unidirectional continuous fibre-reinforced composites are known to possess excellent fatigue resistance in the fiber direction. This is because the load in a unidirectional composite is primarily carried by the fibers that generally exhibit excellent fatigue properties. Hybridization, which may produce significant improvement in the mechanical properties in general, is expected to do so in the fatigue behaviour too, provided that the appropriate design parameters are understood.

Theoretically, it can be predicted that properties of hybrid composites are expressed as proportional contributions from the various components of the hybrid via a "rule-of-mixtures". However, it is well recognized that hybrid composites may exhibit deviations from the "rule-of-mixtures" prediction, known as "hybrid effects". Hybrid effects can be positive or negative, and their magnitudes depend on the layer stacking sequence and on the loading configuration. Our study proposes to investigate the concept of "tailored hybridization" in the fatigue behaviour, with an objective of identifying the parent fibres and the ideal lay-up sequence that together, via hybridization, will produce a positive hybrid effect under fatigue conditions.

A number of features make the fatigue behaviour of composites an intricate subject, one which does not lend itself to a simple analysis. A major difficulty is that fatigue damage mechanisms are complex, involving various combinations of fiber and-matrix damage. Moreover, the statistical nature of defect-dependent processes - which fatigue is - increases the level of complication, by increasing the scatter of the results, hence, demanding a large number of repetitions [5]. Consequently, the models of fatigue of composites are empirical, comprising the static strength, material constants, the cyclic load or strain range, and some measure of the fatigue life, as its fundamental parameters. This is exemplified by Eq. 1, which expresses the empirical observation that the *S-N* curves of composite materials can often be represented by the straight line [6]:

$$\Delta S / \sigma_{tu} = m \log N + b \quad (1)$$

where ΔS is the stress range, σ_{tu} is the ultimate tensile stress, N is the fatigue life, and m and b are material constants.

Another important aspect of fatigue testing is that it combines simultaneous variations of stress, strain and time. The viscoelastic nature of polymer matrix composites - particularly under flexural loading - implies that the strain rate is an important factor. Therefore, the rate effect becomes a relevant issue in the study of fatigue properties of such materials.

The present study combines preliminary investigations of the fatigue behaviour of hybrid composite materials in flexure in two different directions:

An experimental investigation of hybrid effects in the *S-N* trends, as a function of the fibre types and structure of the material; A study of the rate-dependent flexural behaviour and of its correlation with the fatigue life.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental program was carried out with a set of unidirectional materials, comprising the parent aramid fibre (A) and carbon fibre (C) -reinforced composites and sandwich hybrids of aramid/carbon/aramid (A/C/A) and carbon/aramid/carbon (C/A/C) with different ratios between skin and core thicknesses. Full experimental details are given elsewhere [7].

Specimens in fatigue testing and rate effect testing were loaded in three-point bending at relatively high loading span-to-specimen depth ratios, designated to produce tensile/compressive failures. The span-to-depth ratio in fatigue tests was 13.7-17.7 (the loading span was 40 mm, and the loading ratio varied with the depth of the specimen), and in rate effect tests the loading ratio was 14.5-19.0 (with a loading span of 50mm).

Fatigue behaviour was studied by cyclic loading at relatively high stress amplitudes (with ΔS varying from a minimum of 10% to a maximum of 70-100% of the static strength). The specimens were fatigued at low cycling rates (0.05-0.5 Hz) with an Instron Universal Tester. The strain rate effect was tested at cross-head speeds of 10, 5, 0.5, 0.05 and 0.005 cm/min. The strain rates were calculated from the machine crosshead speed according to the equation $\dot{\epsilon} = (6h/L^2) \dot{D}$, where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, \dot{D} is the cross-head speed, h is the specimen thickness, and L is the loading span.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 exhibits typical *S-N* semilogarithmic plots for the two parent composites and for the hybrid sandwiches. The symbol S in Fig. 1 designates S_{max} , which is the maximum of the amplitude of

the cyclic stress, and the arrows mark specimens which did not fail after the specified number of cycles. Straight lines were fitted, considering only the failed specimens, according to the function

$$S = n \log N + a \quad (2)$$

where n and a are material constants.

Fig. 1 Fatigue results of the A and C parent composites and of the ACA and CAC hybrids presented as $S-N$ plots according to Eq. (3).

Apart from the observation that the aramid fibre-reinforced parent composite is the most insensitive to cyclic loading - at much lower stress levels, though - we notice that the ACA results exhibit a bigger scatter compared with the other results, which is attributed to its exceptionally high rate sensitivity.

Another common way to present fatigue results is according to Eq. 1, with the advantage that the stress amplitude, ΔS , is normalised with respect to the ultimate strength of the material. Fig. 2 presents plots of $\Delta S / \sigma_{TU}^{ap}$ vs. $\log N$. It is noted that regardless of the differences between the materials, the average value of m is around 0.1, while b is close to 1 (Table 1), in agreement with the literature [6,8].

Table 1: Experimental Values of Fatigue and Rate-Dependence Constants

Material	Constants				γ (MPa)
	n (GPa)	a (GPa)	m	b	
M	-	-	-	-	2.5
A	0.011	0.56	0.056	0.98	5.9
C	0.081	1.15	0.102	0.96	15.5
ACA	0.063	1.23	0.077	0.93	69.9
CAC	0.115	1.13	0.131	0.95	17.2

As pointed out above, the bending behaviour of aramid fibre-reinforced composites - and under

certain conditions, that of their hybrids too - is dominated by their premature yielding in compression on the compression face, as a result of the low compressive strength of the fibre. It is thought that indeed the rate dependence of the compressive strength is the crucial factor that determines the fatigue behaviour. Accordingly, the ultimate stress on the compressive side, σ_{cu} (also the compressive yield strength), is taken as failure criterion, and is plotted versus the logarithm of the strain rate in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2 Fatigue results of the A and C parent composites and of the ACA and CAC hybrids presented according to Eq. (1), by plotting $\Delta S / \sigma_{tu}^{ap}$ vs. $\log N$.

Fig. 3 The compressive yield stress in flexure as a function of the strain rate.

DISCUSSION

The focal point of the fatigue results in Figs. 1 and 2 is the unique properties of the ACA hybrid. This material presents a positive hybrid effect in its static flexural strength ($a = 1.23$ GPa, Table 1) compared even with the C parent composite (Fig.1). This effect was observed before, and accounted for by a compressive failure stress of the carbon fibre core of $\sigma_{cf} = 1.6$ GPa, which was 33% more than the compressive strength as measured for the parent carbon fibre composite [3]. It was suggested that that hybrid effect could possibly be explained on the basis of the protection from the damaging action of the loading roller, that the aramid fibre skin might give to the brittle carbon fibres, thus, preventing premature failure, as in the C composite. An alternative explanation might be based on the high strain rate dependence of the compressive strength of the ACA hybrid, as discussed below.

The advantage of the very high flexural strength of the ACA hybrid - underlined by the inferiority of the CAC hybrid - comes with a fatigue behaviour which is quite predictable from the properties of the A and C parent composites. Its fatigue life, as presented in Fig. 2, exhibits a value of $m = 0.077$, which is exactly the arithmetical average of the m values of the parent composites.

The reason for higher rate sensitivity of the ACA hybrid is not fully understood. It may derive from the rate sensitivity of the compressive yield strength of the material, which is discussed next.

The viscoelastic time-dependent nature of the compressive yield behaviour of aramid fibre-reinforced composites was described recently [9] according to Eyring's theory [10] by the following relationship:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \epsilon_0 \exp(\sigma_{cu} v / kT) \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_0 is a constant, v is the activation volume, k is Boltzmann's constant and T is the absolute temperature. The Eyring theory is well accepted to describe the rate dependence of the yield behaviour of polymers [11], and has already been used before to express the rate dependence of the compressive stress of glass fibre-reinforced epoxy composites [12]. When the stress sensitivity factor γ , defined as $\gamma = kT / v$, is employed, Eq. 3 can be rewritten as

$$\sigma_{cu} = \gamma \ln(\dot{\epsilon} / \epsilon_0) \quad (4)$$

When σ_{cu} is plotted versus the logarithm of the strain rate, it is possible to estimate γ from the slope of curve. The experimental values of γ , pertinent to the compressive stresses of the materials under the current investigation (Fig. 3) vary typically from 5.9 MPa for the A parent composite to 105.6 MPa for the AC₅A hybrid (Table 1).

The calculation of the σ_{cu} values, which are presented in Fig. 3, took several forms according to the type of the material concerned. In the M material, in the C composite and in the CAC hybrid the elastic model was used. In the latter material, the relative thickness of the elastic carbon fibre skin was 0.29 - exactly the minimum thickness required to ensure elastic behaviour all the way to fracture [3].

The compressive yield strengths of the aramid composites were calculated according to the elastic/plastic analysis proposed in [1,13], and those of the hybrids were calculated by the elastic/plastic model of symmetric hybrids proposed in [3] (see [7]).

Coming back to the results in Fig. 3, the reason for the exceptionally high rate dependence of the compressive strength of the ACA (and the AC₅A) hybrid is still unclear, particularly in the light of the weak rate sensitivity of the compressive strength of the A parent composite. We realize, however, that the outstanding hybrid effect in the strength of the ACA hybrid, as discussed above, may well be a rate dependent effect. With compressive failure being the active mode of failure, both static and fatigue properties are expected to be a direct function of the compressive strength, which in turn is highly strain rate dependent. Therefore, it is possible that the positive hybrid effect for the ACA hybrid will diminish or even disappear as the loading rate is decreased.

CONCLUSIONS

Aramid fibre/carbon fibre hybrids of the ACA type, namely, sandwich hybrids with aramid fibre-reinforced skins and carbon fibre-reinforced core, exhibit a positive hybrid effect in their flexural strength. The high flexural strength of these hybrids is reflected in their higher fatigue stress too, although the fatigue life itself is given by a linear rule of mixtures from the properties of the parent materials. The advantage of the fatigue behaviour of the ACA hybrids is underlined by the inferiority of the CAC materials.

A possible explanation for the positive hybrid effect in the flexural fatigue of the ACA hybrids may lay with the strain rate-dependence of failure in these materials. With compressive failure being the active mode of failure in these materials under both static and fatigue conditions, the respective properties are expected to be a direct function of the compressive strength, which in turn is extremely strain rate dependent. The direct reason for the high strain rate sensitivity is not fully understood yet, and we tend to attribute it to the more pronounced viscoelastic flexural behaviour of the ACA hybrids, as indicated by the incremental stiffness measurements.

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